

Hybrid Hackathon Post-Survey Template

This template contains a collection of measures to assess the perception of hybrid hackathon participants after an event has ended. The template was developed by adapting existing measures from a previous study [1] focused on team dynamics in traditional settings. New measures target hybrid collaboration, covering communication patterns between in-person and remote members, and collaboration dynamics such as task distribution and engagement in hybrid hackathon settings.

We encourage template users to tailor the survey to their specific event needs by adding relevant scales and removing those that are perceived to not be useful. However, it's important to keep the existing scales intact to preserve their integrity.

If you utilize this instrument to study an event, we would appreciate it if you would be willing to share anonymized responses with us. Please contact the main author for further details. This instrument is available on Zenodo and on the Hackathon Planning Kit (<https://hackathon-planning-kit.org/>).

Survey Cover Page

As an attendee of the [HACKATHON_NAME] hackathon, you are invited to complete the following survey. This hackathon is organized by [HACKATHON_ORGANIZERS]. The main purpose of this survey is [SURVEY_PURPOSE].

The questions are mostly multiple choice / agree-disagree and will take approximately [COMPLETION_TIME_IN_MINUTES] minutes to answer. The risks that are associated with this survey are no greater than those ordinarily encountered in daily life. Your decision regarding whether or not to participate in this study will not result in any loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. Your participation in this survey is voluntary, and you may discontinue participation at any time. Your responses will be de-identified and will remain confidential to the study team.

Anonymized responses to this survey might also be shared with a group of researchers at [RESEARCH_GROUP].

If you have any further questions about the survey, please contact [ROLE] [HACKATHON_ORGANIZER_NAME] ([HACKATHON_ORGANIZER_EMAIL]).

I am age 18 or older, I have read and understood the above information, and I wish to participate in the research and continue with the survey.

Yes (continue the survey)

No (end the survey)

Section 1: Previous experience and motivation

The following questions are related to your prior hackathon experience and your motivations to participate in this event.

1. How many hackathons have you participated in the past?

If you cannot recall the exact number, please provide a rough estimate.

- Short Answer (Number)

2. To what extent was your decision to participate in this hackathon motivated by...

	Not at All	To some extent	To a moderate extent	To a large extent	Completely
Having fun					
Making something cool / Working on an interesting project idea					
Learning about [PURPOSE]					
[HACKATHON_THEME]					
Meeting new people					
Seeing what others are working on					
Sharing my experience and expertise					
Joining friends that participate					
Dedicated time to get work done					
Win a prize					

3. If your participation is motivated by other than the above reasons, please describe additional motivations below.

- Short Answer (text)

4. Did you participate in-person, remotely, or both?

In-person

Remotely

Both

Section 2: Teamwork during this hackathon

The following questions are related to your perception of the team you were a part of during this hackathon.

1. What was the name of your team / project? (mandatory)

- Short answer (text or number)

2. How many people were in your team (including yourself)?

- Short answer (number)

3. Did your team use a code repository? If yes, please provide the URL of that repository below.

- Short answer (URL)

4. Did your team use any other online resources to e.g. create documentation? If yes, please provide the URL of that resource below.

- Short answer (URL)

5. Was there a team leader?

A team leader is someone who provides guidance, instruction, direction and leadership to the team.

Yes, I was the team leader.

Yes, someone else was the team leader.

No, there was no clear leader in the team.

6. How well did you know your team members?

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I knew my team members well.					
I have collaborated with some of my team members before.					

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I have been close to some of my team members before.					
I have socialized with some of my team members (outside of this hackathon) before.					

Section 3: Teamwork during this hackathon continued...

The following questions are related to your perception of the team you were a part of during this hackathon.

1. Would you describe your team process as more...

	1	2	3	4	5
(1) Inefficient to (5) Efficient					
(1) Uncoordinated to (5) Coordinated					
(1) Unfair to (5) Fair					
(1) Confusing to (5) Easy to understand					

2. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your GOALS as a team.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I was uncertain of my duties and responsibilities in this team.					
I was unclear about the goals and objectives for my work in this team.					

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I was unsure how my work related to the overall objectives of my team.					

3. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your TEAM.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Everyone had a chance to express his/her opinion.					
The team members responded to the comments made by others.					
The team members participated very actively during our collaboration.					
Overall, the participation of each member in the team was effective.					

4. How did you communicate with the following groups? Please select all that apply.

	Team members that were in-person	Remote team members	Other hackathon participants that were in-person	Other remote participants	Mentors
Face to face					
Email					

	Team members that were in-person	Remote team members	Other hackathon participants that were in-person	Other remote participants	Mentors
Discord					
Other text messengers (SMS, WhatsApp, Facebook messenger, etc.)					
Zoom					
Other video messengers (Skype, Hangouts, etc.)					
Social networks (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, etc.)					
Shared documents (GoogleDocs, Dropbox, Box, etc.)					

5. Was your team a hybrid team comprised of in-person and remote participants?

Yes (continue to next section)

No (skip next section)

Section 4: Hybrid collaboration

The following questions are related to your perception of collaboration within your hybrid team.

1. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements concerning equality and inclusivity in your hybrid team [2].

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Remote and in-person team members contributed equally to the project.					
Both remote and in-person team members participated equally in project discussions.					
Suggestions by remote team members received equal consideration.					

4. Please indicate your level of agreement with the collaboration dynamics within your hybrid team [3].

	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Task assignments differed between remote and in-person team members.					
Remote and in-person team members were proactive in sharing updates about their tasks.					
Interruptions initiated by remote participants were generally received well.					
Discussions were predominantly led by in-person team members.					

Section 5: Your hackathon project

The following questions are related to your perception of the project you worked on during this hackathon.

1. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to your SATISFACTION with your project.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I am satisfied with the work completed in my project.					
I am satisfied with the quality of my team's output.					
My ideal outcome coming into my team was achieved.					
My expectations towards my team were met.					

2. Please indicate your FUTURE INTENTIONS related to your hackathon project.

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I intend to continue working on my hackathon project rather than not continue working on it.					
My intentions are to continue working on my hackathon project					

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
rather than any other project.					
If I could, I would like to continue working on my hackathon project as much as possible.					

Section 6: Hackathon experience

The following questions are related to your perception of this hackathon.

1. How do you feel about your OVERALL EXPERIENCE participating in this hackathon?

	1	2	3	4	5
(1) Very dissatisfied to (5) Very satisfied					
(1) Very displeased to (5) Very pleased					
(1) Very frustrated to (5) Very contented					
(1) Absolutely terrible to (5) Absolutely delighted					

2. What did you like about this hackathon?
 - Long answer (text)
3. What would you wish to be different about this hackathon?
 - Long answer (text)

Section 7: Demographics and individual background

The following questions are about your personal background.

1. How old are you currently?

- 18 to 24
- 25 to 34

- 35 to 44
- 45 to 54
- 55 to 64
- 65 to 74
- 75 or older
- Prefer not to say

2. Are you...?

(Can be replaced by a text entry field: "If you feel comfortable, we invite you to share your gender with us.")

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

3. What is the highest level of formal education that you have completed until now?

- High school diploma or GED
- Some college
- Associate and/or bachelor's degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Professional degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate
- Prefer not to say

4. Do you consider yourself a minority? (For example in terms of background, gender, expertise or in another way)

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

References

1. Nolte, A., Filippova, A., & Herbsleb, J. (2025). A survey instrument for hackathon organizers and researchers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14705828>
2. Standaert, W., Muylle, S., & Basu, A. (2021). How shall we meet? Understanding the importance of meeting mode capabilities for different meeting objectives. *Information & Management*, 58(1), 103393.
3. Neumayr, T., Augstein, M., & Kubicek, B. (2022). Territoriality in hybrid collaboration. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6(CSCW2), 1-37.